

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SAXOPHONE IN UZBEK MUSICAL ART

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of the saxophone as a musical instrument in the Uzbek musical culture. Information about the creation and structure of the saxophone instrument is also presented.

Key words: Musical culture, musical instruments, Saxophone, Adolf Sax, Hector Berlioz, soprano.

Introduction:

The art of music has always been appreciated by our people. The art of playing musical instruments of the peoples of the East has inherited centuries-old traditions in its development, in which the traditional master-student methods are widely developed. That is, this tradition has been passed down orally from teacher to student, father to son for centuries. Therefore, written information about the history of the origin of some musical instruments is rare. But the legends related to their appearance have reached so far.

With the change of times, it is natural that various changes in the music culture will be news. At the beginning of the last century, along with the Russian musical culture, European musical instruments also entered our country. Among them is the saxophone. Here is a detailed description of the saxophone:

Saxophone (French Saxophone) is a wind instrument made of reeds according to the principle of sound production, belonging to the family of woodwind instruments. The saxophone was invented by the Belgian musician Adolf Sax in 1842 and patented by him four years later. Since the middle of the 19th century, the saxophone has been used as a solo instrument in a brass band, to a lesser extent in a symphony, and accompanied by an orchestra (ensemble). It is one of the main instruments of jazz. Also in the pop music genre. The saxophone has a full and powerful sound, a melodious timbre and excellent technical mobility. The invention of the saxophone dates back to the early 1840s. At this time, working in his father's music workshop in Dinant and obtaining several patents, Sax was able to overcome intonation differences between woodwind instruments, fill the timbre gap between them, and create larger and larger music. was looking for replacement ways. The new instrument was presented for the first time at the Brussels Industrial Exhibition in August 1841 under the name "mouthpiece ofhicleid". This instrument had a metal conical

body, a single-reed mouthpiece (derived almost unchanged from the clarinet), the Theobald Boehm ring valve system, but also had a "serpentine" (coiled) shape.

In 1842, Sachs arrived in Paris, where he planned to promote his new invention. On June 12, the composer, Sax's friend and musical innovator Hector Berlioz published an article in the Paris Journal des débats about the new instrument, which first used the name "saxophone" and soon became widespread. Berlioz was also the author of the first composition with the participation of the saxophone - Chorale for voice and six wind instruments, in which, in addition to the saxophone, other instruments developed or improved by the saxophone were used (for example, the bass clarinet). On February 3, 1844, the composer himself directed the work, and in December, the saxophone appeared for the first time in the opera orchestra at the premiere of George Kastner's opera "The Last King of Judea". In the same year, the saxophone was presented at an industrial exhibition in Paris. Describing the events of 1845-1846, Berlioz wrote in his "Memoirs": "The saxophone is a new member of the clarinet family and, moreover, is very valuable, provided that the performers learn to show all its qualities - must now improve their skills. The conservatory has a special place in the education system, because the time is not long before all composers will want to use it".¹

A saxophone is, as a rule, a conical tube made of special alloys (an alloy of copper and zinc), pakfong (the same composition with the addition of nickel). For compactness, the saxophone tube is bent in the shape of a rod. The upper tones of the saxophone (soprano and sopranino) have a short length and therefore are not usually bent. Modern musical instrument manufacturers sometimes produce straight alto saxophones and, conversely, curved sopranos, but this is only used as an experiment. The saxophone is equipped with a complex valve system that closes and opens the holes in the instrument. Their number varies from 19 to 22 depending on the type of instrument.

The sound of saxophone instruments has a specific timbre, a certain range of sounds, and expressive possibilities. At this point, let's think about musical instruments. The quality of the sound of musical instruments often depends on the shape, general structure, device and material used in its manufacture. Musical instruments have been made from reed, bamboo, wood, stone, bone, metal, leather, silk, coconut, gourd, etc. since ancient times. The voicing can be

¹ Berlioz, *Gektor*. Xotiralar / O.K.Slezkina tomonidan frantsuz tilidan tarjima qilingan. A.A.Xoxlovkinaning kirish maqolasi. V.N.Aleksandrova va E.F.Bronfinning tarjima nashri va eslatmalari. - M.: Musiqa, 1967. - 895 b.

changed with the help of additional instruments, performance styles (for example, strumming, flageolet, etc.), some musical embellishments. Its appearance dates back to the first periods of human history, and its perfection is connected with the development of musical art and performance, as well as the development of musical instrument production techniques. Musical instruments are divided into groups depending on sound sources, groups depending on the style of performance (or the mechanism used), and types depending on their special additional signs. Musical instruments are mainly divided into groups of stringed (chordophones), wind (aerophones), leather-covered (membranophones), reed (hemidiophones), plate, electric and electronic musical instruments - idiophones.

Saxophone belongs to the family of wind instruments. All generals and army chiefs knew the importance of drums and percussion instruments in military campaigns. Trumpets and drums have their own role in winning the war, not only with spears, swords, and bows, but by striking terror and thunder into the enemy's heart through his ears.

The saxophone came to Uzbekistan in the last quarter of the 19th century together with Russian military bands.² Currently, he is a member of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan, various pop orchestras and ensembles. In 1990, a saxophone class was opened at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, and later at music colleges. Sh. Esonboyev, B. Shukurov, Y. Zhivayev, B. Murtazoyev, Y. Gulzarov are well-known musicians.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, even today, the saxophone musical instrument has its unique and important place in our musical culture. It is especially widely used in military and percussion orchestras.

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